

Appendix F: Gallery of radial-velocity best fits

Fig. F.1: Radial-velocity fitting. The red-dashed curves represent the model-fit without the additional Gaussian functions, which are included in the blue-solid curves. The shaded region in the Gaussian fit panels represent 50 random draws of the best-fit distributions.

Fig. F.2: Radial-velocity fitting as in Fig. F.1.

Fig. F.3: Radial-velocity fitting as in Fig. F.1.

Fig. F.4: Radial-velocity fitting as in Fig. F.1.

Fig. F.5: Radial-velocity fitting as in Fig. F.1.

Fig. F.6: Radial-velocity fitting as in Fig. F.1.

Fig. F.7: Radial-velocity fitting as in Fig. F.1.

Fig. F.8: Radial-velocity fitting as in Fig. F.1.

Fig. F.9: Radial-velocity fitting as in Fig. F.1.

Fig. F.10: Radial-velocity fitting as in Fig. F.1.